

BANKING AND FINANCIAL PYRAMID ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: Commercial banks are the "vascular system" of the economy, providing the economy with the necessary financial resources by distributing the accumulated savings of the population and business. This mediation is a source of "fuel" for the further development of the economy. A financial pyramid is a way to provide income to the members of a structure by constantly raising funds. It is also known as an investment pyramid. In this case, the income of the first participant is provided by the funds of the second and other participants. This article discusses the views and comments on the activities of the banking and financial pyramid.

Keywords: bank, financial pyramid, activity, business, economy, income, capital.

The Bank's development strategy is aimed at increasing the bank's investment attractiveness and share value by making fuller and more effective use of its potential to further develop and ensure the bank's activities. The main directions of the strategy:

1. Further strengthening the bank's competitive position in key market segments;
2. Increase investment activity and funding in the field of modernization, technical and technological re-equipment of the economy, as well as active participation in the financial support of small business and private entrepreneurship;
3. Corporate business development;
4. Retail business development;
5. Improving the efficiency of the bank's operating model;
6. Development and modernization of the existing information technology infrastructure of the Bank;
7. Expanding cooperation with international financial institutions and foreign banks;
8. Improving the corporate governance system;
9. Development of a risk management system based on modern integrated risk management processes for business;
10. Implement and implement a strong personnel policy.

The financial pyramid is driven by people's desire to get rich quick and make easy money. Financial pyramids say you have to invest in wax first, big interest is promised, you are assured that your money will be returned quickly, you are asked to hire acquaintances to make money, and they will have to invest their own money. A financial pyramid is a way to provide income to the members of a structure by constantly raising funds. It is also known as an investment pyramid. In this case, the income of the first participant is provided by the funds of the second and other participants. The source of these revenues is often not specified. Or declared under false names.

In short, A commercial bank is a credit institution that conducts commercial banking activities, such as raising funds and providing loans, opening and maintaining bank accounts, and making payments. Commercial banks are one of the intermediaries between those who have free money (savings) and those who need it. Commercial banks are the "vascular system" of the economy, providing the economy with the necessary financial resources by distributing the accumulated savings of the population and business. This mediation is a source of "fuel" for the further development of the economy.

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